

PRINCIPAL STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP APPROACH AS CORRELATE OF TACKLING TEACHER CORRUPT PRACTICES IN LAGOS STATE JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between principal strategic leadership approach and tackling of teacher corrupt practices in Lagos State Junior Secondary Schools, Nigeria. The study anchored on the transformational leadership theory which characterized principal ability to inspire, motivate, and empower teachers to achieve a shared vision. Two research questions were raised, and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational design. The population of this study consisted of all 327 junior secondary school principals and 8, 252 teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample size of 600 teachers and 60 principals was selected using quota and simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments titled 'principals' Strategic Leadership Approach Questionnaire' (PSLAQ) and Teachers' Corrupt Practices Questionnaire' (TCPQ) were used for data collection. The reliability consistency of the instruments was at 0.81 and 0.84 coefficient using Cronbach's alpha. The Kendall's tau-b correlation was used to analyse data collected using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings of hypotheses 1, and 2 showed that: a significant relationship existed between principals' strategic leadership approach and teacher corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .694$; $N=660$; $p<0.05$); and a significant relationship existed between principals' disciplinary measure and teacher corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria ($\tau_b = .682$; $N=660$; $p>.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that principals who adopted strategic leadership approaches to empower teachers, encourage collaboration, and foster a positive school culture can reduce the likelihood of corrupt practices. Therefore, it is recommended amongst others that policymakers, school administrators, and stakeholders in education should prioritize the development of strategic leadership skills for principals and school principals should be empowered to adopt a strategic leadership approach that promotes a culture of transparency, accountability, honesty and integrity.

Keywords: Corrupt Practices, Integrity, Principal Strategic Leadership and Teacher Discipline

Introduction

Over two decades, the education sector in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State has seems to be facing many challenges, including teacher corrupt practices, which have undermined the integrity and effectiveness of the principal strategic leadership in the junior secondary school

system. Teacher corruption practices have been a persistent problem in schools, with far-reaching consequences for students, teachers, and the community. Teacher corruption practices observe to be unethical attitudes exhibited by teachers toward achieving personal gain through stealing of school property, bribery, sexual harassment, nepotism, embezzlement of funds and extortion by forcing students or parents to pay for services or favours that are not officially required. Ikoya, (2014) posited that teacher corrupt practices can be influenced by various factors, including school culture, teacher motivation, and accountability mechanisms. This ugly situation seems to be identified as a major obstacle to achieving secondary educational goals and objectives. More so, principals are the head teachers or administrators of junior secondary schools that are responsible for overseeing the academic and administrative operations of the school. Principals as strategic leader, plays a critical role in promoting a culture of integrity and accountability in schools (Hallinger & Heck, 2010).

However, the extent to which principals' strategic leadership approach influences teacher corrupt practices in junior secondary schools remains unclear. Strategic leadership refers to the process of planning, organizing, and influencing others to achieve specific goals and objectives. In the context of this study, the principal strategic leadership approach refers to the deliberate and systematic actions taken by principals in promoting a culture of integrity, honesty, transparency and accountability in schools. This includes setting clear goals and expectations for teachers and students; providing feedback and support to teachers to improve their performance; promoting a culture of collaboration and teamwork among teachers; encouraging open communication and transparency in school operations; and making decisions that promote the welfare and interests of students and teachers. In addition, the components of principal strategic leadership approach in the school system includes strategic thinking; leadership, communication, collaboration and partnerships, emotional intelligence and coaching and development.

Problem of the Study

Over the years, it seems there is a public outcry on the spread of corrupt practices ravaging the educational sector in Nigeria. Incidentally, junior secondary schools in Lagos State observed to have been plagued by various challenges, including teacher corrupt practices, which have undermined the integrity of the school and the effectiveness of principal strategic leadership. Teacher corrupt practices including embezzlement of funds by misuse of school resources for personal gain; bribery by accepting or offering bribes to influence grades, promotions, or other

benefits; nepotism by favoring friends in promotion, or other decisions; cheating and academic dishonesty by assisting students in cheating or falsifying grades; sexual misconduct by engaging in inappropriate or exploitative relationships with students; neglect of duty by failing to perform assigned duties or responsibilities; misuse of authority by using authority to exploit or manipulate students, colleagues, or parents; and verbal abuse by using verbal insults, intimidation, or humiliation to control or manipulate students which are caused due to remuneration package; unbecoming conditions of service, and lack of implementing of teacher professional code of conduct. This ugly situation requires the attention of educational policymakers and school administrator to initiate principal strategic leadership approach for tackling the menace of corruption bedeviled basic education system in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study aims to fill this knowledge gap by investigating the relationship between principals' strategic leadership approach and teacher corrupt practices.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. examine the relationship between principals' strategic leadership approach and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.
2. determine the relationship between principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were raised:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' strategic leadership approach and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.

Literature Review

This study is anchored on the transformational leadership theory (Bass, 1985). The theory is considered one of the most influential and widely researched leadership theories in the field of organizational behaviour. Transformational leaders are characterized by their ability to inspire, motivate, and empower followers to achieve a shared vision. In the context of this study, principals' strategic leadership approach is conceptualized as a form of transformational leadership that promotes a culture of integrity and accountability in schools. Transformational

leadership is a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems (Damirch, et al in Mohammed, Shittu and Lawal, 2019). Transformational leaders are described as holding positive expectations for followers; it increases levels of motivation and morality (Johnson, 2015). Transformational leadership is a style of leadership where the leader works with employees to identify the needed change, create a vision to guide the change, and execute the change (Business Dictionary, 2016). A transformational leader's main objective is to work to change or transform his or her followers' needs and redirect their thinking. It needs charismatic leadership with individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation (Schultz and Schultz, 2016).

It is observed that several literature review highlights the importance of principals' strategic leadership approach in promoting a culture of integrity and accountability in schools. The review also suggests that principals' strategic leadership approach can influence teacher corrupt practices. Strategic leadership refers to the process of guiding, coordinating and directing an organization to achieve its long-term goals and objectives. Principal strategic leaders possess a unique set of skills, knowledge, and abilities that enable them to make informed decisions, allocate resources, and motivate teachers to achieve a shared vision. The attributes of principal strategic leadership including visionary; forward-thinking; decisive; collaborative; adaptable; and results oriented. Principal Strategic Leadership in schools refers to the process of guiding and directing the school to achieve its long-term goals and objectives. A principal with strong strategic leadership skills possesses a unique set of abilities that enable them to make informed decisions, allocate resources, and motivate stakeholders to achieve a shared vision for the school. The responsibilities of a strategic principal in a school involve setting the school's vision and mission; developing and implementing strategic plans; leading and managing change; building and maintaining relationships; and allocating resources. Therefore, principal strategic leadership is crucial in addressing teacher corruption in schools.

Moreover, teacher corrupt practices are unethical, immoral, or illegal behaviour orchestrated by teachers that compromise the integrity of the educational process and the well-being of students for their gain. It seems that these practices can take many forms, including: embezzlement by misuse of school funds or resources for personal gain; bribery by accepting or offering bribes to influence grades, promotions, or other benefits; nepotism by favoring family members or friends in hiring, promotion, or other decisions; cheating and academic dishonesty by assisting students in cheating or falsifying grades; sexual misconduct by

engaging in inappropriate or exploitative relationships with students; neglect of duty by failing to perform assigned duties or responsibilities; misuse of authority by using authority to exploit or manipulate students, colleagues, or parents; and verbal abuse by using verbal insults, intimidation, or humiliation to control or manipulate students; stealing and sexual harassment with students in junior secondary school. Consequently, teacher corrupt practices, on the other hand, have been identified as a major challenge facing educational institutions in Nigeria (Aghenta in Ikoya, 2014). However, Hallak and Poisson in Transparency International (2013) shown that teacher corrupt practices can have negative consequences on student learning outcomes, school culture, and the broader education system. Despite the growing body of research on principal strategic leadership and teacher corrupt practices, there is a dearth of studies examining the relationship between these two variables. This study aims to fill this knowledge gap by investigating the relationship between principal strategic leadership and tackling teacher corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools. In the context of this study, teacher corrupt practices are conceptualized as a form of corruption that undermines the integrity of the educational process.

Methodology

The research design was correlational. The population of this study consisted of all junior secondary school principals and teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample size of 600 teachers and 60 principals was selected using a quota and simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments titled ‘principals’ Strategic Leadership Approach Questionnaire’ (PSLAQ) and Teacher Corrupt Practices Questionnaire’ (TCPQ) were used for data collection. 100 teachers and 10 principals were selected from each of the six Education Districts in Lagos State for the study. The questionnaire is divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and section B contains the 20 items structured around the research questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: “Strongly Agree (SA)”, “Agree (A)”, “Strongly Disagree (SD)” and “Disagree (D)”. The Content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and the reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.81 and 0.84 coefficient using Cronbach’s alpha. The data collected were properly analyzed using Kendall's tau-b correlation coefficient using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between principals’ strategic leadership approach and teachers’ corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.

Variables	Correlations		Principals’ Strategic Leadership Approach	Teachers’ Corrupt Practices
Kendall's tau_b		Correlation	1.000	.694
	Principals’ Leadership Approach	StrategicCoefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	660	660
		Correlation	.694	1.000
	Teachers’ Practices	CorruptCoefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	660	660

Source: Field Survey (2024) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall’s tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between principals’ strategic leadership approach and teachers’ corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between the principals’ strategic leadership approach and teachers’ corrupt practices which was statistically significant ($\tau_b = .694$; $N=660$; $p>0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that “there is no significant relationship between principals’ strategic leadership approach and teachers’ corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria is rejected, and the alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicated the rejection of the null hypothesis. The results indicate that a statistically, significant relationship existed between principals’ strategic leadership approach and teachers’ corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, in Nigeria. This suggests that principals who adopt a strategic leadership approach are more likely to promote a culture of honesty and integrity which can in turn reduce teacher corrupt practices. The findings of this study are consistent with previous research that has highlighted the importance of principal leadership in promoting school effectiveness and reducing corruption (Hallinger & Heck, 2010; Leithwood & Riehl, 2003).

Table 2: Kendall's tau-b correlation analysis between principals’ disciplinary measures and teachers’ corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria.

Variables		Correlations		
			Principals' Disciplinary Measures	Teachers' Corrupt Practices
Kendall's tau_b	Principals' Disciplinary Measures	Correlation	1.000	.682
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	660	660
	Teachers' Corrupt Practices	Correlation	.682	1.000
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	660	660

Source: Field Survey (2024) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

A Kendall's tau-b correlation was run to investigate the relationship between principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a strong, positive correlation relationship between the principals' principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices which were statistically significant ($\tau_b = .682$; $N=660$; $p>.05$). Hence, the hypothesis stated that "there is no significant relationship between principals' principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria is rejected, and the alternate was accepted. The p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between principals' disciplinary measures and teachers' corrupt practices in Lagos State junior secondary schools, Nigeria, suggesting that principals who implement effective disciplinary measures are more like to reduce teacher corrupt practices. The findings are consistent with Bennett & Robinson (2000), posited that disciplinary measures can influence employee behaviour and reduce misconduct in organisation.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the study concluded that principals who adopted strategic leadership approaches to empower teachers, encourage collaboration, and foster a positive school culture can reduce the likelihood of corrupt practices. However, the study highlights the

importance of principals' disciplinary measures in addressing teacher corrupt practices in junior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The principals should prioritize the enforcement of effective disciplinary measures to promote a culture of integrity, transparency, honesty and accountability in school.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Educational policymakers and administrators should prioritize the development of strategic leadership skills among junior secondary school principal
2. School principals should be empowered by policymaker to adopt a strategic leadership approach that promotes a culture of transparency, accountability, honesty and integrity.
3. Principals should develop and implement effective disciplinary measures to address teacher corrupt practices through EFCC and ICPC.
4. Policymakers should provide training and support for principals to develop their disciplinary skills through seminar programme.
5. The ministry of education should monitor the implementation of the already establish policies and procedures for addressing teacher corrupt practices.

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